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PHYSICO-CHEMICAL, ICP-OES, FTIR AND SEM ANALYSIS OF HERBAL DRUG VELERUKKU SAMULA PAMPAM (Calcined oxide form of CALOTROPIS GIGANTEA.LINN)

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Siddha systems of medicine is one of the Indigenous Systems of Medicines (ISM) time tested and followed by the ancient Tamil speaking people for more than 5000 years. *Erukku (Calotropis gigantea)* has anti-inflammatory, anti-pyretic, analgesic, wound healing & antibacterial action. All parts especially leaves are effective in Bronchial Asthma. Approximately 300 million people worldwide currently have asthma which estimates suggesting that asthma prevalence increases globally by 50% every decade. **Materials & Methods:** This herbal preparation *VellerukkuSamoalaparpam (VSP)* was prepared as the herbal pampam to reduce the quantity of medicine and increasing the efficacy and bio-availability as per the literature. The trial drug had proved the safety by its toxicity studies and bronchodilator and antihistaminic pre-clinical studies with the proper IAEC approval. **Results:** The physico-chemical analysis provides proper buffering action and reduces the auto immune activity and Magnesium promotes healthy lung function by acting as a bronchodilator, preventing the bronchial passages from going into spasm. The FTIR and ICP-OES studies strongly showing the safety of the drug by proving heavy metals are in below detectable levels and also the trial drug has high Potassium, Calcium and Magnesium. With the help of SEM, the trial drug consists of particles within 100 to 200 nm in size. **Conclusion:** By this we came to know that the drug has been finished perfectly and able to produce good therapeutic values. Hence this trial drug proved its safety and having the Nano particle in size it is very much useful in the treatments of asthmatic and other -lung diseases.

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INTRODUCTION

Siddha systems of medicine is one of the Indigenous Systems of Medicines (ISM) time tested and followed by the ancient Tamil speaking people for more than 5000 years. It has its own way of treating the diseases like maintaining the equilibrium in the life forces in the body called as *Vali, Azhal* and *Aiyam*. For this three physical elements of the external world, air (wind), heat (fire) and water are considered as the three fundamental humors. In siddha pathology all diseases are caused by the changes in the three cardinal humors wind, bile, and phlegm. That the relative proportion of these humors are responsible for a person's physical and mental qualities and disposition. To treat the diseases Siddhar's used various kinds of medicines in 32 forms for the easy and efficacious manner.

In the hierarchy preparations like *Parpam, Chenthooram, Chunnam, Kattuand Kalangu* are consciously framed as Nano medicines to provide high pharmacological value and low toxic effect when those metals and minerals are therapeutically used^[1]. The great SiddharThirumoolar clearly explained and documented the size of a Nano particle up to 10^{-10} in his various songs. In Siddha system the metal and mineral preparations are very consciously made into Nano particles with '*Pagai*' (antagonist) '*Naipu*' (agonist) drugs to nullify the toxicity and increase the potency respectively^[2].

In this herbal preparation VellerukkuSamoalaparpam (VSP) was prepared as the herbal parpam without using any metals and mineralsto reducing the quantity of medicine and increasing the efficacy and bio-availability. So the shelf life of the drug is increased from 90 days to 100 years. This medicine belongs to the intermediate state between herbal and mineral preparation. By this the medicine has high potency and less side-effect while targeting the disease. *Siddharsused vellaierukkan (Calotropisgigantea.Linn)* as a medicine for longevity. Here the medicine was indicated for the treatment of respiratory diseases and lung infections in the texts of siddhars. Hence, we preferred to test this drug to collect in-depth knowledge to prove it scientifically for the modern world.

The *Calotropis* has several uses from the ancient time. Tannin used as dyestuff: AMacerated bark extract can be used for de-haring hides and tanning. The bark and the latexare widely used as arrow and spear poisons. The latex is cardio-toxic with the active ingredient being calotropin. Latex of *C. procera* is 80 % effective in inhibiting the activity of the tobaccomosaic virus. The leafy branches are said to deter ants. Medicine: Compounds derived fromthe plant have been found to have emeto-cathartic and digitalic properties.

The principal active medicines are asclepin and mudarin. Other compounds have beenfound to have bactericidal and germicidal properties. The latex contains a proteolytic enzymecalled calotropaine. An infusion of bark powder is used in the treatment and cure of leprosyand elephantiasis. It is inadvisable to use bark that has been kept for more than a year.The root bark is an emetic, the flower a digestive, and a tonic is used for asthma. Barkand wood stimulate lactation in cattle. Roots (extremely poisonous) are applied for snakebite.The milky sap is used as a rubefacient and is also strongly purgative and caustic^[3].

The latex is used for treating ringworm, guinea worm blisters, scorpion stings,venereal sores and ophthalmic disorders; also used as a laxative. It's use in the treatment ofskin diseases has caused severe bullous dermatitis leading sometimes to hypertrophic scars.The local effect of the latex on the conjunctiva is congestion, epiphora and local anaesthesia.The twigs are applied for the preparation of diuretics, stomach tonic and anti-diarrhoeotics andfor asthma.Anti-fungal activity of latex suggests that Arka has a promising role in curing skin ailments. The anti-nociceptive activity & analgesic activities of dry latex have been proven^[4]. Arka has anti-inflammatory, anti-pyretic, analgesic, wound healing& antibacterial action.All parts especially leaves are effective in Bronchial Asthma^[5].

Asthma prevalence is rising sharply with increasing urbanization and westernization. Approximately 300 million people worldwide currently have asthma which estimates suggesting that asthma prevalence increases globally by 50% every decade. With the projected increase in the proportion of the world's urban population from 45% to 59% in 2025, there is likely to be a marked increase in number of asthmatics worldwide over the next two decades. It is estimated that there may be an additional 100 million persons with Asthma by 2025^[6].

According to the recently conducted National Family Health Survey (NFHS)-3, the overall prevalence of asthma among adult men and women in India is similar with 1,696 and 1,627 per 100,000 respectively (IIPS and Macro International 2007). The number of men and women with asthma increases steadily with age. Prevalence of asthma is higher in rural areas (1,719 per 100,000 for women and 1,799 per 100,000 for men) than for urban areas and that it is more common among women than men. In the present study, an effort has been made to establish the scientific validity of a *siddha* drug *vellaierukkansamulaparpam*-(*Calotropisgigantea.Linn*) for bronchodilator and antihistaminic property.

This trial drug had proved the safety by its toxicity studies and bronchodilator and antihistaminic pre-clinical studies with the proper IAEC approval by the ethical committee no. XIII/VELS/COL/11/CPSCEA/IAEC/23.09.11. With those results the trial drug clearly indicates its efficacy and safety in the very positive way to prove the siddhar's knowledge are scientifically true.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Vellaierukkansamulam– (*Calotropis gigantea*.Linn fresh whole plant)

Aloe vera Juice – (*Aloe barbadensis* fresh jelly pulp)

Chebulic myrobalan powder (dry *Terminalia chebula* skin powder)

Required quantity of above mentioned fresh herbals were collected from the Herbal garden, Erode, Tamilnadu and dry herbs purchased from TAMPCOL Govt. Raw Drug store Chennai. All the herbs were properly authenticated and certified by Botanist, Siddha Central Research Institute, Chennai-106 and experts of Gunadpadam, PG Department, Government Siddha Medical College, Chennai.

Step I: Collected *Calotropis* raw plant washed thoroughly and cut into small pieces and allowed to dry in shadow for three days then it was completely dried under sun for another 3 days. After the plant dried completely it was burnt in to ashes in an iron vessel. The ash sieved methodically to get the uniform particle size

Step II: *T. chebula* outer skin powdered and Aloevera jelly pulp collected and washed thoroughly. These two were mixed well and kept in a stainless steel plate in inclined position to collect the juice.

Step III: The ash and the juice were added little bit little and grinded well in a stone mortar and pestle until the mixture reaches the pill rolling consistency. Then the paste was made in to equal size of *villai* (lenticular shaped pellets) and allowed to dry in the sun for 2 days.

Step IV: Those completely dried *villai* (lenticular shaped pellets) were subjected in to *Pudam* process in which the drug is kept in shallow earthen plate covered by an identical plate. The mouth is closed by mud pasted cloth and kept in a pit, and heated by using the given number of cow dung cakes. As per the literature in this process *Gajapudam* (1000 Nos. of dried cow dung cakes) were used. Finally the finished product *Velerukkansamulaparpam* (Calcined oxide form) has been kept in an air tight glass container for further research purposes^[7]. Pictures of Raw plant and finished medicines are shown in Fig. 1 & 2.

Fig.1 Fresh plant.

Fig.2 Finished Drug.

Dose: 2- 4 grains (130mg to260mg) twice a day with honey.

Uses: *kasam*, *swasam* (cough and breathing problems) particularly in Bronchial Asthma.

Physico-Chemical Analysis:

The physico-chemical analysis and elemental analysis of this herbal formulation have been done at SAIF (Sophisticated Analytical Instrument Facility) in IIT, Madras, Guindy Campus, Chennai. In this analysis, the trial formulation is subjected to various Physico-chemical parameters for the standardization. The results are exhibited in the Table 1 and 2.

Table 1. Physicochemical properties of *vellerukkusamulaparpam*.

S No.	Parameters	Values obtained (%w/w)	Heavy/ toxic metals	
1	Total ash value	10.21	Lead	BDL
2	Acid insoluble ash	15.23	Cadmium	BDL
3	Water soluble ash	8.54	Mercury	BDL
4	Moisture content	9.16	Arsenic	BDL
5	Foreign organic matter	6.42	Volatile oil	BDL
6	Crude fibre content	18.00		
7	Alcohol soluble extractive	5.6		
8	Water soluble extractive	15.4		

Table 2. Colour, nature and percent yields of extracts of *VelerukkuSamulaParpam*.

S.no.	Extract Solvents	Colour	TLC/GC (PEAKS)	Nature	% Yield (w/w)	pH
1	Water	Light black	6	Solid	40	7.1-7.8

Elemental Analysis Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR)**Instrument Details:**

Model: Spectrum one: FT-IR Spectrometer.

Scan Range: MIR 450-4000 cm^{-1} .Resolution: 1.0 cm^{-1} .

Sample required: 50mg, solid or liquid.

Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) is an analytical technique used to identify mainly organic materials. FTIR analysis results in absorption spectra which provide information about the chemical bonds and molecular structure of a material. The FTIR spectrum is equivalent to the "fingerprint" of the material and can be compared with catalogued FTIR spectra to identify the material. FTIR spectrum analysis is very helpful to identify the presence of functional groups. Characterization of herbal formulations is essential to identify the lead molecule for further research to elucidate the structure of functional compounds which is reasonable for its therapeutic value^[8].

Fourier Transforms Infrared Spectroscopy Analytical Capabilities:

Identifies chemical bond functional groups by the absorption of infrared radiation which excites vibrational modes in the bond. Especially capable of identifying the chemical bonds of organic materials. Detects and identifies organic contaminants, identifies water, phosphates, sulphates, nitrates, nitrites, and ammonium ions useful with solids, liquids, or gases.

The interpretation of infrared spectra involves the correlation of absorption bands in the spectrum of an unknown compound with the known absorption frequencies for types of bonds. This table will help users become more familiar with the process. Significant for the identification of the source of an absorption band are intensity (weak, medium or strong), shape (broad or sharp), and position (cm^{-1}) in the spectrum. The results of FTIR are discussed in graph.

Inductively Coupled Plasma Optical Emission Spectrometry (ICP-OES)

Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry (ICP-MS) also referred to as inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectrometry (ICP-OES), is an analytical technique used for the detection of trace metals. It is a type of emission spectroscopy that uses the inductively coupled plasma to produce excited atoms and ions that emit electromagnetic radiation at wavelengths characteristic of a particular element. The intensity of this emission is indicative of the concentration of the element within the sample. The results are provided in the Table 3& 4.

Table3. Results of VESP in ICP-OES.

S.No	Elements with frequencies	Availability Mg/l
1.	As193.696	BDL
2.	Ca317.933	174.218MG/L
3.	Cd 226.502	BDL
4.	Fe 238.204	30.75mg/L
5.	Hg 253.652	BDL
6.	K 766.490	320.15mg/L
7.	Mg 285.213	28.124mg/L
8.	Na 589.592	83.348mg/L
9.	P 213.6617	27.125
10.	Pb 230.204	BDL
11.	S 181.975	18.235mg/L

BDL- Below Detectable Level.

Table-4 Color characters of the *vellerukkusamulaparpam*.

S.NO	Solvent used	Under ordinary light	Under ultra violet light
1	PPM	Light black	Light black

Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM)

Resolution: 1.2nm gold particle separation on a carbon substrate.

Magnification: From a min of 12x to greater than 1, 00,000 X

SEM picture of VSP, Fig. 4.

The Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) is a microscope that has electrons rather than light to form an image. There are many advantages to using the SEM instead of a light microscope. The SEM has a large depth of field, which allows a large amount of the sample to be in focus at one time. The SEM also produces images of high resolution, which means that closely spaced features can be examined at a high magnification. Preparation of the sample is relatively easy and required very minimal sample to be conductive in SEM.

These salient features of this instrument gave the big advantage in Siddha system to prove that Siddhar's knowledge are certainly amazing by illustrating the Siddha medicines are in Nano particle in size. So, they are absorbed easily and not producing any toxic effects. Also it produces promisingly good result in the treatment of ailments^[9].

RESULTS & DISCUSSION:

FTIR For basic structure related to bonds, Fig. 3.

For basic structure related to bonds**Fig. 3 FTIR: VELLAI ERUKKAN SAMULA PARPAM.**

3924,3579 – the two peaks comes under OH

3189 – OH (3160-3640)

2019- Aromatic combination bands.

1593 – Amines NH (1650- 1580)

1234- CN

984- Alkane

610- CH

The absorbance frequency around 3924- 3579, 3160-3640 cm^{-1} is corresponding to either for O-H of alcohols/ phenols or for N-H stretch of amines. The absorbance frequency around 2019-1593 cm^{-1} arises from the C-H stretch of Alkenes, Alkanes and Aldehydes. 1300-700 skeletal c-c vibrations with Methane.

Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) data shows oxide forms of potassium, calcium, ferrous and sodium. It also shows that the tested drug possesses a good active bond position, which enhances positive activity in the body^[10].

SEM PICTURE OF VELLAI ERUKKAN SAMULA PARPAM FIG :4

Fig.4. SEM picture of Vellai Erukkan Samula Parpam.

In the SEM picture the drug particle size in Nano level AT X50.000 magnification in the 1µm there are 200 to 300 particles present. The trial drug consists of particles within 1 to 100nm in size. By this we came to know that the drug has been finished perfectly and able to produce good therapeutic values.

Interpretation:

The colour of the sample is same in both the ordinary light and UV light, which proves that there is no radio active compounds present in that. The total Ash value is 10.21% w/w, acid-insoluble ash value is 15.23% (w/w), most of the total ash is soluble in acid, so acid-insoluble ash value is very low denoting that it fully gets digested in our alimentary tract without producing any ill effects. Meanwhile, the water-soluble ash value is 8.54% (w/w) and the foreign organic matter is also very low and this proves that it paves no way for the growth of micro-organisms. The crude fiber content is 18.00 % it clearly explains that this medicine can be easily digested and absorbed easily in the gut. Alcohol soluble extractive is 5.6% and Water soluble extractive is 15.4%. After digestion the micro nutrients of the medicine can easily penetrate and able to produce swift and solid results. So this study helps to standardize the preparatory method of this herbo-mineral formulation. By the heavy metal analysis result, it is inferred that all the toxic heavy metals are removed.

Calcium is known primarily for its function as the main mineral component of bones. But calcium has other important functions, some of which are pertinent to asthma. In the presence of calcium, ATPase is activated to hydrolyse ATP and provides an available energy source for muscle contraction^[11]

When asthmatics are put on intravenous fluid repletion in an emergency room situation, potassium is the first component. Magnesium is essential in muscle relaxation after contraction.

Magnesium also plays a key role in the production of energy which is needed by the chest wall muscles and the diaphragm to perform the work of breathing. In a double blind study, individuals with low magnesium levels had an increase in the power of their respiratory muscles after receiving an intravenous infusion of magnesium. It is generally thought that magnesium depletion leads to respiratory fatigue. Magnesium promotes healthy lung function by acting as a bronchodilator, preventing the bronchial passages from going into spasm. Magnesium deficiency may increase vulnerability to allergies by increasing the release of histamine into the bloodstream, increasing allergic reactivity in general. Magnesium has been found to be deficient in many asthmatics during acute attacks, though actual Mg levels may have been lower since blood level measurements do not detect subtle tissue deficiencies. Low dietary intake of magnesium is associated with an increased incidence of asthmatic symptoms, wheezing and reduced lung function. In my drug Ca 174.218mg/L, K 320.15mg/L, Mg 28.124mg/L

My trial drug has high Potassium, Calcium and Magnesium. It strengthens respiratory muscles and facilitates normal contraction and relaxation. It is also contains Fe-30.75mg/L, it boosts the oxygen carrying capacity of the Red Blood Cells and their functions.

The heavy metals like As,Hg,Pb and Cd are reported to be absent in the drug taken for the study. The absence of heavy metals is clearly explains that the raw drugs had not been collected from any contaminated areas and the process of the medicine preparation was perfectly performed as per the guidelines given in the literature. Once again these results are proving that siddhar's prophecy has scientific value.

CONCLUSION

The physico-chemical analysis provides proper buffering action and reduces the auto immune activity and Magnesium promotes healthy lung function by acting as a bronchodilator, preventing the bronchial passages from going into spasm. Magnesium deficiency may increase vulnerability to allergies by increasing the release of histamine into the bloodstream, increasing allergic reactivity in general. Thus this preparation inhibits the complications and increases the quality of life of the affected patients.

The FTIR and ICP-OES studies strongly showing the safety of the drug by proving heavy metals are in below detectable levels and also the trial drug has high Potassium, Calcium and Magnesium. It strengthens respiratory muscles and facilitates normal contraction and relaxation. It also contains Fe-30.75mg/L, which boosts the oxygen carrying capacity of the Red Blood Cells and their functions.

With the help of SEM, the trial drug consists of particles within 100 to 200 nm in size. By this we came to know that the drug has been finished perfectly and able to produce good therapeutic values. By approaching in NDDS, the trial drug will increase the therapeutic value, bioavailability and act as smart drug. Since most of Siddha Nano particle drug has completely absorbed in the mucosal level Nano particles improve the drug delivery to the cells even in cytoplasm and take up these particles easily because of their size and producing promising results in the expected way.

Hence this trial drug proved its safety and having good response in lung parameters also having the Nano particle in size it is very much useful in the treatments of asthmatic and other -lung diseases.

Recommend future Research

Pre-clinical and clinical research of the trial drug was completed and it also shown the good response on the broncho-dilator activity in animal model and appreciable improvement in quality of life of bronchial asthma patients. Further research in anti-microbial and anti-tuberculosis may help to the affected population.

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Conflict of interest

Conflict of interest declared none.

ABBREVIATION

- FTIR - Fourier Transform Infrared spectroscopy.
- ICP-OES- Inductively Coupled Plasma Optical Emission Spectrometry.
- SEM - Scanning Electron Microscope.
- VESP - *Vellai Erukkan Samula Parpam*.
- BDL - Below Detectable Level
- ISM - Indian Systems of Medicines.

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